

DESIGNING WITH FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES TO PROVIDE ENERGY ABSORPTION MECHANISMS IN DAMAGE TOLERANT FORMULA 1 CARS

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ABSTRACT

Unlike conventional metals and alloys, which are characterised by their ductility, homogeneity, and isotropy, fibre reinforced composites are characterised by heterogeneity and anisotropy, and may be brittle. Fibre reinforced composites possess excellent properties along the fibre, but are relatively weak transversely. The fibre orientation, however, is under the control of the designer who thus has the opportunity to tailor specific properties to meet the need of a particular application. This paper will explore the control of constituents within the composite to optimise energy absorption, impact resistance and damage tolerance under the demanding conditions imposed upon Formula 1 cars. Further improvements can be achieved by combining different composites in hybrid forms and through modifications in structural designs.

Damage tolerant materials have slow damage growth rates and can tolerate relatively large amounts of damage, that can be readily detected, therefore the emphasis is on inspection. This damage tolerance is incorporated into the structure by appropriate material combinations, but must be associated with adequate impact resistance to the rigours of the race track. Perhaps the most significant advantage which fibre reinforced composites offer, is energy absorption within the structure and which allows construction of the survival cell to protect the driver.

The testing programme for material assessment will be exemplified by the selection of illustrative fibre, matrix and lay up combinations which have been evaluated using instrumented falling weight impact testing, residual compressive strength measurements and static loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

The degree of progress in the application and acceptance of fibre reinforced composite materials in Formula 1 cars is based upon the availability and maturity of appropriate technology. The structure must meet certain requirements of strength, stiffness, durability, damage tolerance and energy absorption. Satisfaction of these conditions provides a degree of assurance for the integrity, economic life and safety of the structure.

Despite some misconceptions that composites cannot withstand impact loads, correctly used, composites can perform better than metals in absorbing energy. However, these materials are susceptible to the effect of accidental impact damage. This results in significant reductions in residual compressive strength, which currently limits design strain levels to 0.3–0.4%, well below the capability of most fibres. To develop damage tolerant structures, it is necessary to consider the constituents of the composite and their effect upon the damage tolerance.

2. IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

The energy absorbing properties of composite materials may be described in terms of 'work of fracture', which arises from the failure mechanisms occurring during impact. The inherent brittleness of composites ensures that they do not undergo the yield processes characteristic of ductile materials but, on the application of the load, deform elastically up to the point of fracture. A number of modes of deformation are available, the primary energy absorbing ones being:

- a. cracking and fracture of the fibres,
- b. matrix fracture,
- c. debonding (pull-out) of fibres from matrix, and
- d. delamination of the layers making up the structure.

A composite disintegrates both macro and microscopically during an impact event.

The impact resistance of materials and structures can be evaluated using instrumented impact testing apparatus (1). Devices of this type consist of a weighted impactor propelled in 'free-fall' or spring assisted (Figure 1). Velocity measuring and a load transducer are interfaced with a computer in order to measure the parameters and used to characterise the impact event. Energy required to cause damage, load/time and load/deflection histories and total energy absorbed are typical of the data collected.

3. THE DEVELOPMENT OF DAMAGE TOLERANCE

A composite is considered damage tolerant if the threshold for damage initiation is high, the tolerance to that damage high, or a combination. Three criteria are important: damage initiation, damage growth and residual compressive strength. When designing for damage tolerance it is necessary to consider minimisation of the damage and maximisation of residual compressive strength. The development of damage tolerance is very dependent on the materials of the composite: the fibre, resin and interface. It is helpful to consider the critical properties of the fibre, matrix and interface that affect the various forms of damage. The matrix and interface are considered to be the weak links of the composite and consequently have significant influence

upon damage propagation. The properties of the fibre cannot be ignored, because they significantly affect the type of damage formed.

3.1. Damage Initiation

In the impact event, the threshold for damage initiation is dependent upon how much elastic strain energy the composite can absorb. The elastic strain energy can be increased by improving the strength or failure strain of the fibre, the damage threshold is, therefore, increased. The use of fibres with different properties should be considered because of the different effects that the fibres can have upon damage formation. High modulus fibres generally lead to greater stress and strain concentrations in the matrix, and thus lead to the formation of many types of damage. Lower modulus fibres, with higher failure strains, induce more widespread demands on the matrix and thus, may also lead to damage formation.

It is the nature of the damage and absorbed energy associated with it that affects the final selection of the material.

3.2. Damage Propagation

The effect of the matrix properties is significant on the damage propagation in the composite and composites made from tougher resins are generally less susceptible to damage. The interface between the matrix and the fibre is a significant factor in developing a damage tolerant composite. Indeed, early composite materials were notoriously brittle, not only because the matrix was inherently brittle, but also because of a lack of understanding about controlling the interface.

Carbon fibres were, therefore, given an oxidative surface treatment during manufacture to increase the bond strength between the fibre and the matrix. Increased interlaminar shear strength is the result of increased oxidative treatment, although an optimum value is desirable, because a plateau is reached and notched tensile strength *decreases* with increased oxidative treatment, as shown in Fig.2. The fibre surface treatment reduces the intraply splitting and delamination at the notch tip, while reducing the size of damage zone formed, leading to greater residual stress concentrations. This also causes reduced residual tensile strength after impact. Under compressive loading, however, increasing the surface oxidative treatment has a beneficial effect because reduced areas of damage result and delamination growth is restricted.

The damage tolerance of the composite is thus dependent upon the interactions between:

- a. the modulus of the carbon fibre,
- b. the toughness of the resin, and
- c. the selection of an appropriate level of oxidative surface treatment to develop an appropriate interface

3.3. Damage Tolerance

The majority of the work carried out on the improvement of damage tolerance within composite systems has concentrated on either producing higher strength fibres or toughening the resin matrix. The toughening process is usually achieved by creating plastic zones within the matrix

and/or mechanisms to blunt and deflect propagating cracks. This is generally executed by means of thermoplastic second phase additions to the primary resin matrix.

The effect of toughening agents is to increase the work of fracture within the composite. The data collected tend to be comparative rather than quantitative despite the well defined test procedures employed. The reasons for this are firstly, that composite structures are far more complex than the simple laminates evaluated under test, and secondly, improvements in toughness change the nature of the failure from a brittle to a 'pseudo-plastic' mode. Since the theory is based on linear elastic behaviour, any increase in toughness will progressively invalidate the mathematical model by which it is described. Notwithstanding this, a qualitative study at McLaren has shown that the introduction of tougher and tougher resin systems has significantly improved damage resistance and tolerance. Witness to this is borne by the reduction in the amount of damage recorded and a smaller number of repairs being required. Furthermore, over the course of the last two seasons, there have been a number of serious accidents, all of which the drivers survived unhurt.

Damage tolerance is evaluated by inflicting measured levels of impact upon test coupons. Ultrasonic damage maps produced before and after the impact can be used to model the extent and severity of cracking and delamination with respect to the incident energy. Once impacted, the coupons are mechanically tested in order to evaluate the consequential deterioration in properties from which damage tolerance characteristics can be computed. The mechanical testing is generally carried out under compressive loading conditions, as shown in Fig.3, since it is in this configuration that composites are most prone to failure (2).

Advances in computer controlled servohydraulic testing equipment allow very sophisticated assessment of the damage tolerance of composite components and sub-assemblies. Impact damage may be simulated during fabrication or deliberately created using falling weight impactors or some form of projectile. Damaged samples may be subsequently tested either statically to destruction, or dynamically for endurance. Software packages such as Instron's RS.FLAPS (3) can be used to 'play back' service data collected previously at the circuit. Consequently, it is possible to determine whether a damaged component is capable of finishing a race at a particular Grand Prix circuit without it having left the factory! This is extremely useful when testing items such as suspension members whose failure would be catastrophic.

3.4. Energy Absorption

The attainment of high values of specific energy absorption is dependent on the ability to initiate a controlled disintegration process at loads below those required to cause failure of the structure as a whole. The designing-in of mechanisms capable of triggering such processes may well result in structural weakness and the loss of primary strength and stiffness. One possible approach is the use of structural forms which are self triggering. Typical of such a shape would be a tapered tube which would fail at the narrow end with a crack zone moving progressively rearwards. In Formula 1 design, it is rather fortuitous that components such as the chassis and nose cone require to be made in this shape anyway to satisfy aerodynamic profiling. Experimentation has shown that the fibre fracture mode of deformation is the most efficient in absorbing energy. The use of high strength fibres, which would improve damage tolerance, tends to lower the energy absorbing efficiency. The reason for this is that high strength fibres tend to induce a delamination failure rather than local fracturing of the component.

3.5. Compression After Impact

Residual compressive strength after impact is a key design parameter, and is often design limiting. Low impact energies, can result in delamination if the properties of the constituents of the composite are not optimised and this causes a fall in compressive strength due to local ply instabilities (4). At higher impact energies, fibre damage is also incurred and further reductions in residual compressive strength also occur. Optimum properties are not always available in a single fibre–matrix system, and work carried out at McLaren and TWI suggests that hybridisation offers significant improvements in damage tolerance, with reduced damage areas and improved residual properties (5). The combination of ultra high modulus fibres with high strength fibres offers the designer significant benefits for stiff, reduced weight energy absorbing structures.

4. IMPACT CONSIDERATIONS IN FORMULA 1 MOTOR RACING

During the course of a race a Formula 1 car is likely to be subjected to a number of different forms of severe impact loading. These events include strikes from track debris (stones, pieces broken off other cars etc.), collisions of various types and impact with the track due to a combination of bumps and perturbations with the aerodynamics of the car driving it groundwards. Since the early 1980s the construction of Formula 1 racing cars has been dominated by the use of carbon fibre reinforced composite materials (6).

When carbon fibre composite chassis were first introduced by McLaren, in conjunction with Hercules, a number of designers expressed concern as to the suitability of such brittle materials in a dynamic application. Indeed, some even went so far as to attempt to have them banned on safety grounds! An incident in the 1981 Italian Grand Prix at Monza went a long way to dispelling these fears and removing the doubt as to the safety of carbon fibre structures under impact. John Watson lost control of his McLaren MP4/1, smashing heavily into the Arco barriers. The ferocity of the crash was sufficient to remove both engine and transmission from the chassis. The remains of the monocoque were catapulted several hundred yards along the circuit until finally coming to rest. Watson was able to walk away from the debris completely unscathed. The wrecked chassis (Figure 4) clearly demonstrated the ability of the composite structure to absorb and dissipate kinetic energy. The high stiffness of the chassis allowed the impact to be absorbed by the structure as a whole rather than being concentrated at the point of impact. Furthermore, the composite material, was able to absorb the energy of impact by a controlled disintegration of the structure. By contrast, the forces generated from the impact of a vehicle constructed from a ductile metal such as aluminium are sufficient to exceed the material's elastic limit. Had Watson been driving such a car the monocoque would have remained in one piece, but collapsed until all of the energy had been absorbed. He would doubtless have been killed.

One does not need to delve very far into the available literature to realise that the dynamic response of both materials and structures are very poorly understood. It is becoming increasingly necessary to include impact resistance in the design of a great many engineering systems. This requirement has been emphasised recently in the UK, following inquiries into engineering disasters (7,8).

That composite racing cars are safer and more damage tolerant than their metal predecessors is without doubt. The factors which govern that behaviour are however, very much misunderstood. Over recent years the public have become accustomed to seeing drivers emerge unscathed from what appear to be horrific accidents. Indeed, the cynics amongst us might suggest that such crashes are enjoyed as much as the racing! A degree of complacency about drivers safety has developed within the media, but the serious injuries incurred by Martin Donnelly in the 1990 Spanish Grand Prix bear witness that the design philosophies and materials physics of composite structures cannot cope with all eventualities.

One of the most attractive features of composite materials in engineering design is the ability to exploit their anisotropy in tailoring of their mechanical properties to suit a specific application. It is not unreasonable to postulate that the energy absorbing properties may also be tailored to provide an optimum performance. It is very doubtful, however, that the arrangement best suited to mechanical properties will be the same as that designed for impact resistance. The number of 'crash-configurations' possible during a race is almost limitless such that optimisation for crash worthiness can really only ever be a matter of empiricism, experience and common sense. A number of design procedures have been developed in tandem with changes in the sport's regulations, with the express aim of improving the impact performances of the cars and hence safety and survivability. The techniques and tests employed however are a product of evolution and experience rather than any rigid scientific analysis.

5. DESIGNING WITH COMPOSITES IN FORMULA 1

In common with aircraft, the composite components of a Formula 1 car are stiffness critical. That is to say they are designed to transmit rather than absorb, the various loads generated during operation. Carbon fibres exhibit the highest specific stiffness of any widely available engineering materials. Since stiffness is the major design criterion one might expect materials selection to be a simple matter of choosing fibres with the highest modulus. Unfortunately, producing fibres of increasing modulus involves a corresponding increase in brittleness (9).

The vast majority of the car's outer surface is designed to optimise aerodynamic behaviour. The efficiency of the various aerodynamic devices depends critically on the boundary layer at the surface. Disruption of this boundary layer caused by, for example, holes punched in lightweight body work, will thus clearly have an adverse effect.

Figure 5 shows an impacted high modulus carbon fibre composite. The low strength and elongation of this material result in fibre fracture being the primary mode of deformation, with most of the damage confined to the locality of the impact. Figure 6, on the other hand, is a micrograph illustrating damage in a high strength 'intermediate modulus' fibre composite. High fibre strength and increased strain-to-failure have resulted in delamination and fibre pull out being more dominant failure modes. It is interesting to note that the total energy absorbed in the two cases is very similar. This would seem to suggest that, although very susceptible to impact damage, high modulus fibre structures ought to be safe in terms of crash protection.

Designers of composite structures have long been aware of the dangers that relatively small amounts of impact damage can cause, resulting in significant reductions in mechanical properties. Within the sphere of Formula 1, the designer must satisfy three criteria with regard to impact

damage. The first is damage resistance, that is to say that the component must withstand an impact strike with a minimum amount of damage incurred on the composite. The second condition is that of damage tolerance, in other words the ability of a material to be damaged and yet still able to function within the defined loading régime. With this in mind we will discuss two individual components that have been designed to meet each of these points and one major component that must withstand both cases. The final consideration is that of energy absorption, which is probably the most important factor since it governs the safety of the driver in a crash situation (10).

5.1. Track Rods

The function of this component is to form the link between the steering rack to the road wheel. It is positioned foremost in the suspension set up and therefore susceptible to impact from track debris. Projectiles can reach velocities of up to 180ms^{-1} when accelerated off the rear wheel of an opponents vehicle.

The property required by this component is that of damage tolerance. The use of relatively low modulus fibres is the key to it's success. The high strain to failure ensures that damage is passed through the matrix encompassing the fibres, rather than damaging the fibres themselves, hence fibres remain intact and are therefore capable of sustaining load.

Due to the simplicity of this component it was decided that the manufacture of unrepresentative test coupons was ill advised, therefore all testing was carried out on actual components. Compressive and tensile strength and stiffness were measured in an Instron 4500 static loading frame on undamaged components. As well as the static loading, actual track data, from instrumented track rods was played back through an Instron 8500 servo hydraulic test frame. The data may be manipulated to include a 30% safety margin. Whilst not strictly necessary, this gives both the drivers and designers confidence. Composites are also sensitive to the frequency of loading, and the use of actual track data therefore covers the frequency spectrum encountered in service. With this database, track rods were subjected to 10 impacts along their length, using a steel ball bearing 3mm in diameter fired from a nitrogen charged gas gun at an average velocity of 250ms^{-1} . Each of the impacted specimens was then subjected to a repeat of the previous tests to measure the residual strength, stiffness and mechanical performance under track conditions. With satisfactory test results the composite track rods were used throughout the 1992 racing season and are in use now.

5.2. Nose Cone

The governing body (FISA) of Formula 1 issues a set of requirements each year regarding a number of safety features on each vehicle. One such regulation stipulates that the nose cone should be able to withstand a frontal impact of 11ms^{-1} under race conditions i.e. with a simulated engine weight, fully laden with fuel and dummy driver. The chassis under test must experience an average deceleration of no more than 25g, and there must be no damage to any part of the structure behind the line of the drivers feet. In this application, damage resistance is unimportant, indeed the more damage dissipated in the form of micro and macro fracture means the required amount of energy can be more easily absorbed by the structure as a whole.

The research programme instigated to investigate the optimum design for this component was once again based on the true item, as they are relatively easy to manufacture and test. The overall geometry of the nose cone structure is that of a cone, thus implying that as the structure is crushed, the cross sectional area of the damage zone increases resulting in a proportional increase in the deceleration. However, incorrect use of material could mean that the damage is not allowed to progress through the cone rendering the geometrical design useless and resulting in extremely high deceleration forces. At the other extreme, a composite with too high a modulus could result in the entire nose cone collapsing and damage continuing into the chassis (home of the drivers feet!). The use of intermediate modulus (IM) fibres was found to make the nose cone too strong and it therefore failed by delamination, transmitting energy into the chassis with resulting damage.

5.3. The Chassis

The chassis, also known as the survival cell, is also subjected to a number of tests prior to it being deemed fit for race use. This requires the chassis to be made from a damage resistant material i.e. carbon fibres of relatively low modulus and high strain to fail. However, torsional rigidity is of paramount importance to this major component, requiring the use of high modulus fibres that are inherently brittle (low strain to fail). A compromise must be sought. For the chassis test programme it was impractical to produce actual chassis for testing. An approach of compression after impact testing on a variety of laminated composites was decided upon.

The chassis has a number of ancillaries attached to it that are of major importance not least of which is the engine, other components include suspension pick up points and front and rear wing assemblies. In modern Formula 1, complex computer simulations, known as aeromaps, are used to predict the behaviour of a car under a variety of conditions. The computations cannot predict chassis distortion due to the inherent variations in stiffness from structure to structure and the continually varying loading sequence. We are however able to minimise such errors. The major contributor to chassis distortion is the engine itself. This power plant produces roughly 700bhp and is held to the back of the chassis by four aerospace grade bolts. Essentially the engine is constantly trying to 'unscrew' itself from the rest of the vehicle, and any energy that successfully distorts the chassis is wasted. It is important that as much energy as possible is transferred direct to the road wheels. This requires very high torsional rigidity and leads us to the use of very high modulus fibres, in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction.

In the 0 and 90 degree fibre direction, no significant increase in torsional rigidity can be achieved, but as stated earlier this is not the only criterion to be taken into account. A total of six static tests must be carried out on every chassis prior to racing. On the first chassis more severe loads are applied as a worse case scenario. This is not undertaken on every chassis as damage may be incurred that could cause subsequent failure during a race. To overcome the applied test loads, fibres of higher strength must be employed within the lay-up to dissipate this energy. Such Hybrid laminates give the required torsional modulus whilst the higher strength fibres protect the ultra high modulus fibres. Therefore, the structure has good damage tolerance.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Designing to provide for energy absorption in Formula 1 motorsport requires that the engineer know exactly how he wishes the component to react to different impact conditions. The

components outlined above are clearly defined for a particular application and have proven successful in service. Areas of research that will require further investigation are those of temperature effects on impact resistance/tolerance and projectile velocity effects.

Impact performance is a topic which is fraught with misconceptions, not just in Formula 1, but throughout industry as a whole. The regulations governing the crash worthiness of Formula 1 cars, for example, consist mainly of the application of static proof loads to determine impact resistance (aside that is from a true impact requirement for the nose cone). Since the impact behaviour, and hence driver survivability, of composite materials and structures are very 'strain rate dependant', tests of this type are inappropriate other than to define a minimum level of structural integrity. Impact testing should be considered.

A Formula 1 car is by necessity extremely complex. Consequently it is very doubtful if impact testing will ever provide more than qualitative or, at best, semi-quantitative data, especially considering our present lack of understanding. Notwithstanding this, the testing carried out to date at McLaren and TWI has yielded significant improvements in damage resistance and tolerance. Additionally, a better understanding of impact performance has created the possibility of using composites in more dynamically loaded components within the suspension and transmission.

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Fig.1 Instrumented falling weight impact testing.

Fig.2 The effect of carbon fibre surface treatment and hence fibre/matrix bond strength on the interlaminar shear strength of a unidirectional CFRP composite and on the notch sensitivity of a $[0_{2r} + 45_{2r} - 45_{2r} 0_{2s}]_s$ CFRP laminate.

Fig.3 Residual compression strength testing.

Fig.4 The wrecked chassis from the McLaren MP4/1.

Fig.5 Impacted high modulus carbon fibre composite.

Fig. 6 Impacted high strength intermediate modulus composite.